

The Impact of Foreign Directors, Executive Character, Institutional Ownership, and Auditors on Tax Avoidance: Leverage as an Intervening Factor

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Abstract: This study aims to determine the effect of directors with foreign experience, executive character, institutional ownership and audit committee on tax avoidance with leverage as an intervening variable. The research method used is a quantitative method with time series data from 2017 to 2019. The population used in this study is all manufacturing companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange for the period 2017-2019. The method of collecting samples using purposive sampling method. The number of samples used as many as 36 companies. The analytical method used is multiple linear regression and path analysis. The results of the analysis show that in equation I, there is a direct effect of the variable director with overseas experience (DLN), executive character (KE) and leverage (DER) on Tax Avoidance. Meanwhile, the variables of executive character (KE) and institutional ownership (KI) do not have a direct influence on Tax Avoidance. In equation II, it is known that there is a direct effect of the variable of directors with overseas experience (DLN) and institutional ownership (KI) on leverage (DER), while the variables of executive character (KE) and the Auditor (A) do not have a direct influence on leverage. (DER).

Keywords: Director with overseas experience (DLN), executive character (KE), institutional ownership (KI), Auditor (A), Leverage (DER), Tax Avoidance (TA)

I. INTRODUCTION

Taxation is one of the sources of state revenue that plays a significant part in paying all government expenditures and necessities for people's prosperity (Nugraha and Mulyani 2019). According to Article 1 of Law Number 16 of 2009 Concerning General Provisions and Tax Procedures, paragraph 1, taxes are necessary contributions to the state owing by persons or businesses that are coercive under the law, without direct remuneration, and are utilized for state objectives.

A corporate entity is one of the parties that contribute significantly to tax income, yet the government's aim of maximizing tax collection frequently contradicts the firm's goal as a taxpayer. Taxes are assumed to be a cost for the corporation. This creates a conflict of interest between the tax authorities and the firm, with the tax authorities as the main (stakeholders) wanting as much tax revenue as possible, and the company as an agent wanting the tax payment to the state to be as low as feasible. Taxpayers work hard to limit the amount of tax that must be paid. Taxes do not give a direct counter-achievement to the taxpayer, thus the taxpayer wishes to minimize his tax burden in order to maximize his profit.

Based on agency theory, differences in interests between tax authorities and firms will encourage taxpayers or corporate management to engage in tax planning, one of which is tax evasion. Tax avoidance is an activity taken to decrease or limit tax responsibilities by meticulously arranging things in such a manner that loopholes in tax regulations are exploited. Tax evasion is considered to not violate tax regulations since taxpayers strive to lower the amount of tax owing by seeking for flaws (grey areas) in the legislation (Pohan, 2016).

According to (Suardana 2014) institutional ownership, independent commissioners, audit quality, audit committee, return on assets, executive character, and leverage all have an impact on tax evasion. According to (Dewi 2019), corporate governance influences company engagement in tax evasion techniques via the president director. As a leader,

the director has the authority to make choices that affect the company's operations; hence, experience is one of the most significant qualities that a director must possess. According to stakeholder theory, the director's position is critical in deciding strategic decisions for the organization (Ghozali and Chariri, 2007). According to the study's findings (He, Chen, and Chiang 2015), a Director with foreign expertise influences goal orientation, time frame, problem definition, information management, and strategic decisions, including tax avoidance.

In addition to having a board of directors with international expertise, executive character is a factor that influences tax avoidance. (Nugraha and Mulyani 2019) According to (Nugraha and Mulyani 2019), executives with risk aversion will engage differently in tax avoidance tactics than executives with risk-taking qualities. (Carolina, Maria, and Debbianita 2014) argues that if a CEO is more risk-taking, the potential of tax avoidance increases. According to research (Nugrahitha and Suprasto 2018), (Oktamawati 2017), Rahmawati (2017), (Feranika 2016), and (Swingly and Sukartha 2015), executive personality has a beneficial influence on tax avoidance.

Another element influencing tax evasion is the existence of a supervisory mechanism overseen by the audit committee/auditor (Dewi 2019). According to (Fadhilah 2014), the audit committee is a committee that works professionally and independently with the assistance of the board of commissioners, and their duties are to assist and strengthen the function of the board of commissioners or supervisory board in carrying out the oversight function on the financial reporting process, risk management, audit implementation, and corporate governance implementation in companies. An audit committee is appointed, dismissed, and reports to the board of commissioners. Because all companies that go public on the IDX form and have an audit committee chaired by an independent commissioner, the board of commissioners has supervisory authority and can influence company management to prepare correct financial reports. Finance has an impact on tax management, particularly tax avoidance.

According to Feranika and Mukhzarudfa (2017), leverage is another element that might influence tax avoidance. The ratio of long-term debt to total assets is referred to as leverage (Feranika and Mukhzarudfa 2017). (Oktamawati 2017) Companies that employ debt will have to pay interest. Loan interest is a deductible cost against taxable income under tax laws, specifically Article 6 paragraph 1 of Law No. 36 of 2008. Deductible interest expenditure reduces the taxable earnings of the corporation. The lower taxable earnings will eventually reduce the amount of tax that the corporation must pay (Sari and Harto 2014). Tax avoidance is carried out through policies implemented by the business's leaders, where company leaders as decision makers and policies implemented by corporations have a key impact in the amount of corporate tax evasion, such as deciding company funding in the form of debt or leverage.

Based on prior inconsistency, the authors are interested in doing study on "The Influence of Foreign Directors, Executive Character, Institutional Ownership, and Auditors Against Tax Avoidance: Leverage as an Intervening Factor." The goal of this research is to "examine and identify the impact of the Director of Foreign Affairs, Executive Character, Institutional Ownership, and Auditor on Tax Avoidance as an Intervening Factor."

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Agency theory describes how agency relationships develop when one or more persons (principals) engage another person (agent) to deliver a service and then transfer decision-making authority to the agent (Jensen and Meckling, 1976). Agency theory is a theory that underpins the practice of firms publishing annual reports to shareholders (Handoko, 2013), (Andriyani and Mudjiyanti 2017).

According to stakeholder theory, the firm is not an entity that functions just for its own advantage, but must also help its stakeholders. Shareholders, creditors, consumers, suppliers, the government, society, analysts, and other groups are among these stakeholders (Ghazali and Chariri, 2007).

Hypothesis Development and Conceptual Framework:

H1: Director with international expertise has an impact on tax avoidance.

H2: The Executive Character has an influence on Tax Avoidance.

H3: Institutional ownership has an impact on tax evasion.

H4: An auditor's impact on tax evasion exists.

H5: Leverage has an influence on tax avoidance.

H6: There is an influence of Director with overseas experience on Tax Avoidance through Leverage as Intervening variable.

H7: There is an effect of Executive Character on Tax Avoidance through Leverage as an Intervening variable.

H8: There is an effect of Institutional Ownership on Tax Avoidance through Leverage as an Intervening variable.

H9: There is an effect of Auditor on Tax Avoidance through Leverage as Intervening variable.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Methodologies

This study employs quantitative research in the form of a hypothesis test. This study makes use of secondary data derived from publishing reports of manufacturing businesses listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX).

Method of data collecting

The yearly financial statements for the 2017-2019 period, as well as other material linked to research variables, were analyzed for data collection in this study utilizing library research and documentation methodologies.

Sample Population and Research

During the 2017-2019 period, this study makes use of secondary data in the form of an annual report. This information was gathered from the IDX database (www.idx.co.id). This study's population consisted of all manufacturing businesses registered on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) between 2017 and 2019. Purposive sampling is used to determine the sample.

Methodology of Analysis

The regression analysis approach was employed in the analysis. The computation employs statistical methods, which are aided by the SPSS application. In this study, descriptive statistical analysis, the classical assumption test, and multiple linear regression analysis utilizing the following regression equation:

Equation I:

$$TA = \alpha + \beta_1 DLN + 2KE + \beta_3 KI + \beta_4 A + 5DER + e$$

Equation II:

$$DER = +\beta_1 DLN + 2KE + \beta_3 KI + 4A + e$$

Equation III:

$$TA = +\beta_5 DER + e$$

Description:

TA	= Tax Avoidance
DLN	= Overseas director
KE	= Executive Character
KI	= Institutional Ownership
A	= Auditor
DER	= Leverage
$\beta_{1,2,3,4,5}$	= Regression Coefficient
e	= errors.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1V.I Analysis Results

Based on the results of the analysis, it is known that the results of statistical testing on the variables used in this study are as in table 1 below:

Table 1. Descriptive Statistical Analysis Test Results

Variable	N	Min	Max	mean	Standard Deviation
DLN	36	0.099	1,947	0.75003	0.417341
Executive Character	36	0.018	0.082	0.04736	0.017607
Institutional Ownership	36	0.328	0.969	0.62936	0.168282
Auditor	36	1,000	4,000	2.9444	0.53154
Leverage	36	0.099	1,947	0.77228	0.465813
Tax Avoidance	36	0.012	0.897	0.29008	0.224946

Source: Processed data (2021).

Classic assumption test

Based on the research results, it is known that the results of the classical assumption test in this study are as follows:

1) Data Normality Test Results

Table.2 Data Normality Test Results

Test	Kolmogorov- Smirnov Z	asymp. Sig. (2- tailed)	Description
Equation I	0.920	0.336	Normal distributed data
Equation II	0.871	0.434	Normal distributed data

Source: Processed data (2021)

Based on the results of the data normality test using the One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, it is known that in equation I, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z value is 0.920 and the Asymp value. Sig. (2- tailed) of 0.336. Then in equation II, the value of Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z is 0.871 and the value of Asymp. Sig. (2- tailed) of 0.434. Because Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) in equations I and II is greater than 0.05 (0.651>0.005), it can be concluded that all data used in this study are normally distributed.

2) Multicollinearity Test

Based on the results of the analysis, it is known that the results of the multicollinearity test are as follows:

Table. 3 Multicollinearity Test Results of Equation I

Variable	Tolerance	VIF	Description
DLN	0.731	1.368	Multicollinearity does not occur
Executive Character	0.860	1.163	Multicollinearity does not occur
Institutional Ownership	0.770	1,298	Multicollinearity does not occur
Auditor	0.953	1.050	Multicollinearity does not occur

Source: Processed data (2021)

Based on the results of the multicollinearity test in table 3 above, it is known that in equation I, all independent variables have a tolerance value > 0.10 and VIF <10. So it can be concluded that all the data used in this study are free of multicollinearity.

Table 4 Multicollinearity Test Results Equation II

Variable	Tolerance	VIF	Description
DLN	0.954	1.048	Multicollinearity does not occur
Executive Character	0.873	1,146	Multicollinearity does not occur
Institutional Ownership	0.878	1,138	Multicollinearity does not occur
Auditor	0.961	1.041	Multicollinearity does not occur

Source: Processed data (2021)

Based on the results of the multicollinearity test in table 4 above, it is known that in equation II, all independent variables have a tolerance value > 0.10 and VIF <10. So it can be concluded that all the data used in this study are free of multicollinearity.

3) Autocorrelation Test

Autocorrelation was tested using Runs Test. Based on the results of the analysis, it is known that the results of the autocorrelation test in this study are as shown in table 5, as follows:

Table 5. Autocorrelation test results with *Runs Test*

Test	asympt. Sig. (2-tailed)	Description
Equation I	0.866	There is no autocorrelation
Equation II	0.612	There is no autocorrelation

Source: Processed data (2021)

Based on the results of the autocorrelation test using the Runs Test in table 5 above, it is known that the magnitude of the Asymp value. Sig. (2-tailed) in equation I and equation II is greater than 0.05. So, it can be concluded that there is no autocorrelation in equation I and equation II.

4) Heteroscedasticity Test

Heteroscedasticity in this study was tested using the Spearman-rank test or the Spearman Rho test, which correlates the absolute residuals from the regression of all independent variables. If the probability of the correlation result is less than 0.05 (5%) then the regression equation has heteroscedasticity problems and vice versa. The results of the heteroscedasticity test using the Spearman Rho test are as follows:

Table 6. Heteroscedasticity Test Results Equation I

Variable	Sig. (2- tailed)	Description
DLN	0.608	There is no heteroscedasticity
Executive Character	0.647	There is no heteroscedasticity
Institutional Ownership	0.805	There is no heteroscedasticity
Auditor	0.609	There is no heteroscedasticity
Leverage	0.519	There is no heteroscedasticity

Source: Processed data (2021)

Based on the results of the heteroscedasticity test using the Spearman Rho test in table 6, it is known that the value of Sig. (2-tailed) on all variables in equation I is greater than 0.05. So, it can be concluded that there is no heteroscedasticity problem.

Table 7 Heteroscedasticity Test Results Equation II

Variable	Sig. (2- tailed)	Description
DLN	0.442	There is no heteroscedasticity
Executive Character	0.511	There is no heteroscedasticity
Institutional Ownership	0.868	There is no heteroscedasticity
Auditor	0.710	There is no heteroscedasticity

Source: Processed data (2021)

Based on the results of the heteroscedasticity test using the Spearman Rho test in table 7, it is known that the value of Sig. (2-tailed) on all variables in equation II is greater than 0.05. So, it can be concluded that there is no heteroscedasticity problem.

IV.II Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing in this study was carried out using multiple linear regression and path analysis. The results of the multiple linear regression test in this study are as follows:

Multiple Regression Test Results.

Table 8 Multiple Regression Test Results

Variabel	Equation I			Equation II			Equation III		
	B	<i>t</i> _{hitung}	Sig.	B	<i>t</i> _{hitung}	Sig.	B	<i>t</i> _{hitung}	Sig.
(Constant)	0,077	0,401	0,691	0,895	1,892	0,068	0,053	0,919	0,364
DLN	0,177	2,344	0,026	0,530	3,079	0,004	0,307	4,810	0,000
KE	-3,817	-2,308	0,028	-2,896	-0,679	0,502			
KI	-0,184	-1,005	0,323	-0,930	-2,089	0,045			
KA	0,075	1,436	0,161	0,069	0,509	0,614			
DER	0,202	2,929	0,006						
F _{hitung}	7,886	Sig.F	0,000	3,259	Sig.F	0,024	30,251	Sig.F	0,000
R ²	0,568			0,296			0,405		
Adjusted R ²	0,496			0,205			0,387		

Source: Processed data (2021)

Based on the results of hypothesis testing in table 4.9, multiple linear regression equations can be arranged as follows:

a. Equation I

$$TA = 0.077 + 0.177DLN - 3.817KE - 0.184KI + 0.075A + 0.202 DER + e$$

Based on the results of the multiple regression test in the above equation, it can be interpreted as follows:

The variables Director with abroad experience (DPLN), Executive Character (KE), Institutional Ownership (KI), Audit Committee (KA), and Leverage (DER) have a positive constant value of 0.077, according to the findings of the regression test in equation 1. This demonstrates that assuming the variables of Director with abroad experience (DPLN), Executive Character (KE), Institutional Ownership (KI), Audit Committee (KA), and Leverage (DER) to be equal to zero has an effect on boosting tax avoidance (Tax. avoidance).

b. Equation II

$$DER = 0.895 + 0.530DLN - 2.896KE - 0.930KI + 0.069KA + e$$

Based on the results of the multiple regression test in the above equation, it can be interpreted as follows:

The variables Director with abroad experience (DLN), Executive Character (KE), Institutional Ownership (KI), and Audit Committee (KA) have a positive constant value of 0.985, according to the findings of the regression test in equation II. This demonstrates that assuming the variables of Director with Overseas Experience (DLN), Executive Character (KE), Institutional Ownership (KI), and Audit Committee (KA) to be equal to zero has an effect on Leverage (DER).

c. Equation III

$$TA = 0.053 + 0.307 DER + e$$

Based on the results of the multiple regression test in the preceding equation, the Leverage (DER) variable has a positive constant value of 0.053. This demonstrates that if the Leverage (DER) variable is assumed to remain constant, the Leverage (DER) value of tax avoidance (Tax Avoidance) will be positive. The positive regression coefficient for the Leverage (DER) variable is 0.307. This means that for every additional value Leverage variable (DER), the value of tax avoidance (Tax Avoidance) increases by 0.307. In the other direction, for every one reduction in the value of the Leverage (DER) variable, the value of tax avoidance (Tax Avoidance) decreases by 0.307.

Analysis Results Discussion

1. The Impact of Foreign Directors on Tax Avoidance

According to the findings of the research, the Director variable with abroad experience (DLN) has a p-value significance of 0.026. Because the p-value significance value is less than 0.05 ($0.026 < 0.05$). Then H_0 is accepted, indicating that the Director variable with foreign experience (DLN) has a direct influence on tax evasion. As a leader, the director has the authority to make choices that affect the company's operations; hence, experience is one of the most significant qualities that a director must possess. According to stakeholder theory, the director's position is critical in deciding strategic decisions for the organization (Ghozali and Chariri, 2007).

2. The Influence of Executive Personality on Tax Avoidance

According to the findings of the research, the Executive Character (KE) variable has a p-value of significance of 0.028. Because the p-value significance value is less than 0.05 ($0.028 < 0.05$). So H_0 is acknowledged, implying that the Executive Character (KE) has a direct impact on tax evasion. The executive character depicts the behaviors made by firm executives when confronted with a danger. The decisions made will reveal whether or not the executive is willing to take chances (Lewellen 2006).

3. The Impact of Institutional Ownership on Tax Evasion

Based on the findings of the investigation, it is known that the Institutional Ownership (KI) variable has a p-value of 0.323. Because the p-value significance value is larger than 0.05 ($0.323 > 0.05$). Then H_0 is rejected, indicating that Institutional Ownership (KI) has no direct influence on tax evasion. Firm management must consider the interests of

institutional parties in addition to the interests of the company. This is reinforced by the stakeholder hypothesis, which claims that the stakeholders decide the company's existence. Because of the company's management's moral commitment to the stakeholders, the company will consider the interests of stakeholders. This moral commitment will encourage the company to formulate a company strategy, and the company's strategy will affect the achievement of the company's financial performance (Ghozali and Chariri, 2007).

4. Auditor Influence on Tax Avoidance

According to the analysis findings, Auditor (A) achieved a significant value of p-value of 0.161. Because the p-value significance value is more than 0.05 ($0.161 > 0.05$). So H_0 is denied, implying that Auditor (A) has no direct influence on tax evasion (Dewi, Ni Nyoman Kristiana; Jati 2014).

5. The Influence of Leverage on Tax Avoidance

According to the findings of the research, the Leverage (DER) variable has a significant value of p-value of 0.006. Because the p-value significance value is less than 0.05 ($0.006 < 0.05$). So H_0 is acknowledged, implying that Leverage (DER) has a direct impact on tax evasion. Based on the route analysis results, the size of the effect of Leverage (DER) on Tax Avoidance is 3.860.

6. Foreign Directors' Influence on Tax Avoidance Through Leverage as an Intervening Variable

According to the path analysis results, the direct effect of the Director variable with abroad experience (DLN) on Tax Avoidance is 0.329. Meanwhile, the indirect effect of the Director variable with international experience (DLN) on Tax Avoidance by Leverage is ($0.475 \times 0.419 = 0.199$). The size of the direct effect of the Director with abroad experience (DLN) on Tax Avoidance is bigger than the magnitude of the indirect influence ($0.329 > 0.199$), based on these findings. As a result, it is possible to infer that leverage has not been established as an intervening variable in the link between the Director with Overseas Experience (DLN) and Tax Avoidance.

7. The Influence of Executive Personality on Tax Avoidance through Leverage as an Intervening Variable

The Executive Character variable (RISK) has a direct effect of -0.299 on Tax Avoidance. Meanwhile, the indirect effect of Executive Character (RISK) on Tax Avoidance by Leverage is ($-0.109 \times 0.149 = -0.046$). According to these findings, the direct influence of Executive Character (RISK) on Tax Avoidance is bigger than the indirect effect ($-0.299 > -0.046$). As a result, it is possible to infer that leverage has not been demonstrated to be an intervening variable in the link between Executive Character (KE) and Tax Avoidance.

8. As an intervening variable, the effect of institutional ownership on tax evasion through leverage.

According to the path analysis results, the direct effect of the variable Institutional Ownership (KI) on Tax Avoidance is -0.137. Meanwhile, the magnitude of the variable Institutional Ownership (KIndirect)'s influence on Tax Avoidance by Leverage is ($-0.336 \times 0.149 = -0.141$). According to these findings, the direct effect of Institutional Ownership (KI) on Tax Avoidance is bigger than the indirect effect ($-0.137 > -0.141$). As a result, Leverage has been demonstrated to be an intervening element in the link between Institutional Ownership (KI) and Tax Avoidance.

9. The impact of auditors on tax evasion using leverage as an intervening variable

According to the path analysis results, the size of the direct influence of the Auditor variable (A) on Tax Avoidance is 0.177. While the size of the Auditor variable (Aindirect)'s influence on Tax Avoidance by Leverage is ($0.078 \times 0.149 = 0.033$). According to these findings, the size of Auditor (Adirect)'s effect on Tax Avoidance is bigger than the magnitude of the indirect influence ($0.177 > 0.033$). As a result, it is possible to conclude that leverage is not an intervening variable in the connection between Auditor (A) and Tax Avoidance.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the tests, it is discovered that in equation I, there is a direct influence of the director variable with overseas expertise, executive character, and leverage on Tax Avoidance. Meanwhile, auditor characteristics and institutional ownership have no direct impact on tax evasion. In equation II, it is recognized that leverage is demonstrated to be an intervening variable between institutional ownership and tax avoidance, but it is not proven to be an intervening variable between foreign directors, executive character, and auditors on tax avoidance.

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